

The Form of Goddess Sarasvatī in the Vedic Samhitās and Her Later Reimagining

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Goddess Sarasvatī has been praised and prayed to in the Ṛgveda in about eighty mantras. She has often been referred to in the prayers to Viśvedevāḥ but she is also a deity of vedic hymns to whom at least three sūktas are dedicated. However, in one-third of the mantras of the last two sūktas, Sarasvatī has been glorified. Sarasvatī has been exalted by Vedic worshippers in the popular fashion and style with which all other Vedic gods are lauded. Thus, in many qualities she is analogous to others but at the same time her individuality can be well-marked in Vedic prayers and mantras sung in her praise. She was conceived in her various aspects by the Vedic seers.

Sarasvatī is, primarily, a river-goddess, though this form of the goddess has not been recognized by scholiasts save Yaska. In the Nirukta, Yaska identifies two distinct categories of mantras associated with Sarasvatī: (i) those that depict her as a river, and (ii) those that revere her as a goddess. This concise formulation by Yaska indicates an awareness of both the natural and the divine dimensions of Sarasvatī's identity, encompassing her dual manifestation as a physical river and as a transcendent deity. By the term *devatā*, Yaska may be understood to designate Sarasvatī either as a river-goddess, as the goddess of learning and intellect, as a deity of the atmospheric region with water as her primary element, or as a composite figure embodying all these aspects simultaneously. Yet the evidence suggests that Yaska most likely conceives of her primarily as a river-goddess. This is indicated by the *mantras* he cites and explicates in support of her characterization, which consistently reflect her riverine identity. Of the two *mantras* quoted by Yaska, the first in which Sarasvatī is described as *pāvakā* ("the purifier"), does not convey any distinctive theological attribute beyond her purificatory function, further reinforcing the interpretation of Sarasvatī as essentially a river-deity in Yaska's exposition.

In the second mantra., however, the distinctive attributes of Sarasvatī are more explicitly delineated. Yaska interprets the passage to mean that Sarasvatī, through her activity (*ketunā karmaṇā*), causes her mighty flood (*maho arṇah sarasvatī*) to become manifest, and that she, by her radiance, reveals with clarity (*pracetayati ketunā*) the entirety of profound knowledge (*sarvāṇi prajñānāni*). Thus, according to Yaska, Sarasvatī is not only a river-deity but also a divine power who, while retaining her riverine character, discloses and illuminates the manifold branches of learning.

After it, Yaska says that Sarasvatī denotes the sense of speech i.e. Vāk- *vaktīti vāk*, *vaceh ucyate 'nayā iti vāk*. She is, therefore, considered as Mādhyamika Vak by the etymologists. Mantras quoted by Yaska refer to Vak in the form of Thunder and Lightning.

"sa no samurjam duhānā dhenurvāgasmannupa suṣtutaitu.."¹

This observation of Yaska leads us to infer, that Sarasvatī was considered by the etymologists to be a goddess of atmospheric region also and in this form she was identical to the goddess Vāk, representing the phenomena of thunder and lightning. Thus it is said generally, by the interpreters of Yaska that the latter too, like Nighaṇṭu took Sarasvatī in two forms - as a river, and as a goddess of atmospheric region holding her sway on the branches of knowledge. However, if we read between the lines of the text of

Yāska, we see that he, perhaps, him-self conceived Sarasvati as nadī-devatā, 'the river goddess', presiding over different branches of knowledge.

Among the Vedic goddesses, Sarasvatī holds a preeminent place, being revered with equal devotion even to this day. She is the goddess of knowledge, art, and culture. In the Vedic hymns, Sarasvatī is primarily manifested in three dimensions as a deity, as a sacred river, and as the divine power of speech (Vāk). The Vedic seers envisioned her as the flow of wisdom, the presiding force of speech, and the sanctifying river.

Within the Ṛgveda, Sarasvatī occupies a distinct and exalted position among the deities. On the one hand, she is revered as a river-goddess, while on the other, she is venerated as the primordial source of knowledge, speech, and learning. The conception of Sarasvatī gradually evolved from her riverine aspect into that of the bestower of wisdom. In the Vedic hymns, she is extolled as the embodiment of immortality, the source of inspiration, and a symbol of purity and creative power. In later developments, this very conception becomes fully crystallized in the Upaniṣads, Purāṇas, and Smṛti literature, where Sarasvatī appears in her complete divine form.

Her name is first encountered in the *Ṛgvedic Samhitā*, where she is primarily the personification of the river Sarasvatī. Throughout the entire Āryāvarta, this river was regarded as the most sacred. Rising from the Himalayas and flowing into the Arabian Sea, Sarasvatī nourished the very heartland of Vedic civilization. The great sacrificial rites of the Vedic age were performed upon her banks. The central region of Āryāvarta, known as Brahmāvarta (corresponding to the modern Kurukṣetra), lay in the tract between the Sarasvatī and her tributary, the Dṛṣadvatī.

In the First Maṇḍala of the Ṛgveda, Sarasvatī is invoked as the goddess of speech (*Vāk-devī*). She infuses wisdom and discernment into the human mind, grants success in the chanting of the Veda and in the performance of sacrifice. The Vedic seer extols her as sanctifying, as the bestower of sustenance through sacrifice, and as the giver of wealth in the form of sacrificial rewards. Here, Sarasvatī is praised simultaneously as the flowing river and as the embodiment of knowledge. As the producer of noble and truthful speech, she becomes the benefactress of human understanding. Flowing forth abundantly, Sarasvatī not only generates waters but also awakens the highest forms of knowledge and inspiration within humankind-

*“Pāvakāh nah sarasvatī vājebhirvājīnāvati. Yajñam vaṣṭu dhiyāvasuh..
Codayitrī sunṛtānām cetantī sumatīnām. Yajñam dadhesarasvatī”..²*

In the *Ṛgveda*'s Second Maṇḍala, a more nuanced and philosophical interpretation of Sarasvatī becomes evident, wherein her threefold dimensions *Mātrī* (Mother), River, and Goddess—are simultaneously manifest. Here she is not merely a natural force but a metaphysical principle, embodying the generative potency of life, the fecundity of nature, and the awakening of higher consciousness through knowledge.

The hymns dedicated to her are articulated as invocations for prosperity and plenitude, wherein she is extolled as “the foremost among mothers, the foremost among rivers, and the foremost among goddesses.” This triple epithet signifies her exalted status both within the natural and the divine orders, situating her as the integrative symbol of nurture, sustenance, and transcendence. In this Vedic vision, Sarasvatī thus emerges as a unifying archetype—simultaneously maternal, elemental, and divine—mediating between the material and spiritual domains of existence.

*“Ambitame nadītame devitame Saraswati.
Aprāśastā iva smasi praśastimanva nskṛdhi”..³*

In the Ṛgveda, three complete hymns are dedicated to Sarasvatī. Beyond these, numerous individual verses also invoke her, from these attestations it becomes evident that Sarasvatī was conceived not

merely as a mighty river of immense physical force, but also as the inner power of knowledge dwelling within human consciousness. She is the divine presence upon whom the seers relied in the act of hymn-composition and sacrificial worship.

One vivid description portrays her as the river in tumultuous surge, whose roaring waters, like a force uprooting the very roots of the lotus, break through the flanks of mountains with their irresistible waves. The Vedic mantra celebrates this formidable, two-shore-destroying Sarasvatī, extolling her through song and sacrifice as both a natural and a divine power, sustaining creation and inspiring sacred utterance.

*“Iyam śuṣmehhivirsakhā ivārujat sānu girīṅām taviṣebhirūrmibhih.
Pārāvataḡhnīmavase suvṛktibhih sarasvatī mā vivāsema dhītibhih”..⁴*

This very hymn of the Ṛgveda is traditionally known as the *Sarasvatī Sūkta*. In it, the seer not only extols the majesty of Sarasvatī in her riverine manifestation but also delineates her as resplendent, endowed with manifold virtues, and as the very embodiment of knowledge. Thus, the hymn simultaneously preserves her natural grandeur as a life-sustaining river and elevates her to the status of a luminous divine principle, radiating wisdom and creative potency.

“Ratha iva vṛhatī vibhvane kṛtopastutyā cikituṣā sarasvatī.”..⁵

In the Brāhmaṇa period, however, a remarkable transformation takes place: the river-goddess Sarasvatī is transfigured into the goddess of speech. From this time onward she comes to be known as Vāgdevī. Expressions such as “*Vāk vai Sarasvatī*” or “*Vāk eva Sarasvatī*” occur repeatedly, making explicit the semantic identity between the two terms. Thus, in the *Jaiminīya Brāhmaṇa* we read: the rite of initiation, the bath is performed on the southern bank of the Sarasvatī; they proceed to Sarasvatī. Indeed, Sarasvatī is Speech itself.

The history of this transformation is of profound interest. In the Ṛgveda itself, alongside Sarasvatī, there is also mention of a distinct goddess named Vāk, though in only one hymn—the celebrated Devī Sūkta. This hymn is particularly significant, for it contains the latent seed of later Śākta traditions. There, Vāk is extolled as the divine sovereign of speech, the cosmic power that underlies and animates all creation. As an example of spiritual mantras, Ācārya Yāska refers to the Devī Sūkta, wherein the seer is Ambhṛṇī, the inspired vision of Vāk herself.

- This naturally gives rise to the question: why did these two goddesses Sarasvatī and Vāk- ultimately merge into one?
- Two principal reasons may be identified:
 1. Although Vāk was originally a distinct deity, Sarasvatī had already been associated with *dhī* (intellect, insight) in the *Ṛgveda*. For instance, it is said: “*dhīnām avitry avatu*” 6/61/7 “May she, the helper of thoughts, protect us.” Since speech cannot exist apart from intellect, it was natural that Sarasvatī should eventually be assimilated into the identity of Vāk.
 2. There were also geographical considerations. As mentioned earlier, Vedic sacrifices were performed on the banks of the Sarasvatī. Since the chanting of hymns also took place upon her shores, the attributes of Vākdevī could easily and naturally be transferred to Sarasvatī herself.
- In the Seventh Maṇḍala, Sarasvatī as river-goddess is praised as the *Ādiśakti*, the primal power. She is celebrated as the vital current of nature, the mother of civilization, and the purest among rivers. Flowing alone from the mountains to the sea, she bestows abundant riches upon the world. This is vividly expressed in Ṛgveda, where her precedence over all other rivers is affirmed. In this hymn, she is described as fair and radiant, the embodiment

of purity, to whom the sacrifice prays both for nourishment and for the preservation of well-being through her beneficence.

*“Ekā cetat sarasvatī nadīnām śuciryatī giribhya ā samudrāt”.*⁶

*“Vardha śubhre stuvate vājānyūyam pāta swastibhih sadā nah”.*⁷

In the celebrated *Nadī Sūkta* of the Tenth Maṇḍala, Sarasvatī is portrayed in a composite form, uniting both of her essential aspects - river and speech. She is conceived as the mother of civilization in its dual dimensions: the material flow that sustains life and society, and the spiritual current that nourishes thought and expression. Thus, she embodies not only the physical vitality of a mighty stream but also the intellectual and cultural vitality of human consciousness.

The seer-poet describes Sarasvatī as forceful and dynamic, comparable in her irresistible surge to the Sindhu, yet distinct in her capacity to bind intelligence to intelligence, thereby fostering the continuity of wisdom across generations. Within the hymn, she is extolled as the foremost among rivers, the guiding current from which others derive inspiration and strength.

Significantly, the hymn invokes the Gaṅgā by name and, through her, offers collective praise to the sisterhood of rivers. In this way, the poet sacralizes the entire river-system of Āryāvarta, situating Sarasvatī at its center as both physical benefactress and metaphysical source of order, culture, and creative power. The *Nadī Sūkta* thus preserves in a single poetic vision the fusion of Sarasvatī’s dual nature: the inexhaustible river that nourishes the earth, and the luminous goddess of speech who sustains the sacrificial word and the civilizational spirit-

“Imam me gaṅge yamune Sarasvati śutudri stomam sacetā puruṣṇyā.

*Asiknyā marudvṛdhe vitastayājīrkīye śṛṇuhyā suṣomayā”.*⁸

In the Atharvaveda, Goddess Sarasvatī is invoked and propitiated as a protective deity for the expulsion of various diseases. It is noteworthy that the Atharvavedic corpus contains a substantial number of hymns associated with magical-healing practices, conventionally designated by the indigenous term *Bhaiṣajyānī*. These incantations and ritual utterances, intended for the alleviation of disease, are variously addressed either to the maladies themselves, conceived anthropomorphically as demonic agents or to the malevolent spirits regarded as the progenitors of such afflictions.

Alongside these, however, there exists another significant category of hymns wherein deities, both gods and goddesses, are invoked to exert their divine power in the dispelling of disease and in the restoration of health. Within this framework, Sarasvatī emerges as a healing force, embodying not only her role as a river of purification and a source of vitality but also as a divine sovereign capable of subduing pathological forces and ensuring the well-being of the devotee.

Within the *Atharvavedic* tradition of magical-healing rites (*Bhaiṣajyānī*), the goddess Sarasvatī is invoked specifically for the destruction of worms, which are conceived as agents of disease. In this context, she is entreated in conjunction with the dual divinity *Dyāvā-Prthivī*, as well as with Indra and Agni, to exercise her power in annihilating these harmful beings. One such invocation declares:

“Ote me Dyāvā-Prthivī, oṭā devī Sarasvatī.

*Otau ma Indraścāgniśca krimīn jambhayatāmiti”.*⁹

Furthermore, Sarasvatī is also invoked in prayers directed toward the general well-being of the infant, underscoring her role not only as a deity of knowledge and speech but also as a benevolent guardian of health and human welfare.

The identification of Sarasvatī with *Vāk* (deified speech) appears to be in a formative stage in the *Yajurveda*, where *Vāk* is still represented as an instrument in the hands of Sarasvatī, through which she exercises her healing power on behalf of Indra.

In the texts of the *Yajurveda*, we occasionally encounter phrases such as:

“Vācā vācam Sarasvatīm”¹⁰
“Vācam Viṣṇum Sarasvatīm”¹¹
“Sarasvatyā vaca”¹²

At first sight, these expressions might suggest compound formulations such as *Vāk-Sarasvatī* or *Sarasvatī-Vāk*. However, when examined within their respective contexts, it becomes evident that *Vāk* here denotes a distinct entity and is not to be understood as fully identified with *Sarasvatī*. Nevertheless, these usages do reveal a stage in the gradual process of convergence between *Sarasvatī* and *Vāk*. They attest to the increasing closeness of the two divinities, while simultaneously preserving their individuality. The distinct status of *Vāk* as an independent deity is further confirmed in passages such as those of the *Aśvamedha*, where the victims consecrated to different gods include separate offerings for *Sarasvatī* and for *Vāk*.

In light of this evidence, it may be concluded that although in the *Yajurveda* *Vāk* had drawn significantly nearer to *Sarasvatī*, their complete identification had not yet been affected, since both continued to exist as separate deities within the Vedic pantheon.

In the *Medha Suktam*, Goddess *Sarasvatī* is invoked in the form of Goddess *Medhā*, who personifies intelligence, wisdom, memory, and the power of discrimination. *Medhā Suktam* is a hymn dedicated to this personified intelligence, and because Goddess *Medhā* is considered a form of *Sarasvatī*, the *suktam* is often chanted as a prayer for learning and wisdom from *Sarasvatī* herself. The *Medhāsūkta*, preserved in the *Taittirīya Āraṇyaka* represents a profound invocation of *Medhā* (intelligence, wisdom, and discernment), wherein Goddess *Sarasvatī* emerges as the principal divine source of cognitive and spiritual faculties. Unlike her early Vedic depiction primarily as a river deity in the *R̥gveda*, the *Medhāsūkta* emphasizes *Sarasvatī*'s epistemic and intellectual dimension, identifying her explicitly as *Medhādevī*-

*“Medhām ma Indro dadātu, medhām devī Sarasvatī,
medhām me Aśvināv ubhādhattām puṣkarasrajā...”¹³*

Here, the aspirant petitions *Indra*, the *Aśvins*, and the goddess *Sarasvatī* for *medhā*. *Sarasvatī* is thus positioned as the primary source of wisdom, while other deities contribute complementary divine support. This underscores her role as the internal faculty of intellect crucial for understanding and retaining sacred knowledge-

*“āmām medhā surabhir viśvarūpā hiranyavarṇā jagatī jagamyā|
ūrjasvatī payasā pinvamānā sā mām medhā supratikā juṣantām”¹⁴*

The *Medhāsūkta* reflects a pivotal transformation in Vedic religiosity, wherein *Sarasvatī* transcends her original riverine identity to emerge as an abstract embodiment of intellect and wisdom. She comes to represent the internalized power of knowledge, learning, and eloquence, a conceptualization that anticipates her later *Purāṇic* portrayal as the ultimate patron of learning, arts, and culture—adorned in white, holding the *Vīṇā* and sacred texts, symbolizing both cognitive and creative mastery.

In the *Medhāsūkta* of the *Yajurveda Saṁhitā*, *Sarasvatī* is conceptualized as *Medhādevī*, the Goddess of wisdom, insight, and eloquence. This hymn signifies a pivotal development in Vedic thought, transitioning her from a natural and riverine deity to a principle of cognition and learning, thereby laying the foundation for her enduring role as the Goddess of knowledge, arts, and culture in later Hindu tradition.

In the Vedic period, Goddess *Sarasvatī* was primarily revered as a river deity. In the *R̥gveda*, she appears as *Nadītamā*—the most resplendent and sacred of rivers, and at the same time as the presiding deity of *Vāk* (speech), the fountain of wisdom, intellect, and insight. Over the course of time, *Sarasvatī* was transformed from a river goddess into the embodiment of knowledge (*vidyā*), learning, and cultural refinement. In present-day life, *Sarasvatī* is not merely an object of religious devotion but has become the universal symbol of education, art, and culture.

In the Ṛgveda She is extolled as the life-sustaining river, the best among mothers, rivers, and goddesses. Gradually, however, she transcends her aquatic form and emerges as *Brahmavādinī*, the goddess of speech and wisdom.

In the Purāṇas, Sarasvatī becomes fully established as the goddess of learning, music, and arts. She is invoked as *Vāk-devī*, consort of Brahmā, and *Vidyādāyinī*. The river-aspect of the goddess recedes into the background, while her divine intellectual and cultural dimensions come to prominence.

In contemporary India, Sarasvatī has emerged as a living symbol of learning and education. She is revered in schools, universities, and libraries as the divine patroness of knowledge, and students continue to invoke her blessings at the beginning of their studies and before examinations. Beyond the academic sphere, she also occupies a central place in the cultural imagination. Musicians, dancers, and artists honor her as the mother of melody and rhythm, seeing in her the divine source of inspiration that nourishes music, theatre, and the fine arts.

The festival of Vasantapañcamī, popularly known as Sarasvatī Pūjā, reflects this enduring presence by uniting communities across social and regional boundaries. Celebrated as a festival of learning and creativity, it has assumed the form of a universal cultural event that transcends sectarian divisions. In the modern era, Sarasvatī has come to represent more than just the sanctity of traditional learning. She functions as a universal emblem of education, embodying the democratization of knowledge and the human quest for enlightenment. Within today's digital age, her symbolic resonance extends further, as she is imagined as the divine bearer of wisdom transmitted through technology, continuing to inspire intellectual and creative pursuits in ever-evolving forms.

References

1. Ṛgveda 8/100/11
2. Ṛgveda 1/3/10-11
3. Ṛgveda 2/41/16
4. Ṛgveda 6/61/2
5. Ṛgveda 6/61/13
6. Ṛgveda 7/95/2
7. Ṛgveda 7/95/6
8. Ṛgveda 7/75/5
9. Atharvaveda- 5/23/1
10. Kriṣṇa-Yajurveda 21/58
11. Kriṣṇa-Yajurveda 9/27
12. Kriṣṇa-Yajurveda 10/30
13. Kriṣṇa-Yajurveda 10/41/3
14. Kriṣṇa-Yajurveda 10/41/5

Bibliography

1. Bloomfield, Maurice. *Sacred Books of the East, Vol. 42: Hymns of the Atharva-Veda*. Translated by Maurice Bloomfield, Clarendon Press, 1897.
2. Griffith, Ralph T. H., translator. *The Hymns of the Ṛgveda*. 2 vols., Motilal Banarsidass, 1973 (original 1896).

3. Jamison, Stephanie W., and Joel P. Brereton, translators. *The Rigveda: The Earliest Religious Poetry of India*. 3 vols., Oxford University Press, 2014.
4. Keith, A. B. *Religion and Philosophy of the Veda and Upanishads*. Harvard Oriental Series, vols. 31–32, Harvard University Press, 1925.
5. Macdonell, A. A. *Vedic Mythology*. Strassburg, 1897.
6. Monier-Williams, Monier. *Religious Thought and Life in India: An Account of the Religions of the Indian Peoples*. London: John Murray, 1883.
7. O’Flaherty, Wendy Doniger. *The Rig Veda: An Anthology*. Penguin Books, 1981.
8. Sarma, D. S. *Studies in the Vedic River-Goddess Sarasvatī*. Indian Institute of Advanced Study, 1996.
9. Thite, G. U. *Sacred Rivers in Indian Culture*. Pune: University of Pune, 1987.
10. Dutta, Rameshchandra & Bandopadhyay, Hiranmay. *Veda, Vol-1-4*: Haraph Prakashani, 2019.